

Synthesis of 2,7 Di [α,γ -Diaminobutyric] Gramicidin S.

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Cyclic decapeptide (L-Val-L-Dab-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ has been synthesized.

A S part of a study of the antibacterial activity of a synthetic decapeptide related to Gramicidin S., (L-Val-L-Dab-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ was synthesized. This cyclic decapeptide differs from Gramicidin S in which the ornithine residue in position 2, 7 are replaced by α,γ diamino butyric residue. Z-L-Dab (γ phth)-ONP¹ was condensed with the tripeptide L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe² to give the corresponding tetra peptide Z-L-Dab(γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (I). The penta peptide Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (II) was obtained by condensation of Z-L-Val-ONP³ with the hydrobromide of the tetra peptide (I). The penta peptide Z-L-Val-L-Dab-(γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (II) was hydrolysed to the corresponding Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OH (III), and the latter using dicyclo-hexylcarbodiimide and p-nitrophenol was converted to its p-nitrophenyl ester (IV). The linear decapeptide Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂OMe (V) was obtained by condensation of Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-ONP (IV) with HBr. L-Val-L-Dab(γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe. The resulting decapeptide (V) was hydrolysed to the corresponding Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂OH (VI), and the latter using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide and p-nitrophenol was converted to its p-nitrophenyl ester (VII). The carboxy group of the decapeptide Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ONP VII was eliminated by using HBr/CH₃COOH, and the resulting (L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ONP, HBr was converted to the required cyclic decapeptide (L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ VIII by cyclization. The phthalyl group of the protected cyclic decapeptide VIII was removed by hydrozoinolysis to give (L-Val-L-Dab-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ IX.

The structure of decapeptide IX was confirmed by its analytical data and by amino acid analysis after its hydrolysis with 6N HCl at 110° for about 24 hr. and some antibacterial testing are under consideration.

Experimental

The time allowed for the completion of the reaction and the purity of the prepared compounds was controlled by means of thin layer chromatography (T.L.C.) using freshly prepared solvent (butanol-water-acetic acid 62 : 2 : 12). Melting points were uncorrected.

Preparation of Z-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (I): To a solution of Z-L-Dab (γ phth)-ONP¹ (0.11 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml), L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe₂ (0.35 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml) was added. After 18 hr. at room temperature, the solid was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, water 5% NaHCO₃, ether, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give Z-L-Dab(γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (0.5 g, 82%), m. p. 203°-5°, R_F 0.45 [α]_D²⁰ = -61 (C=1, in D. M. F.) (found : C, 65.29 ; H, 6.19 ; N, 9.35 ; C₄₁H₄₇N₅O₉ requires C, 65.33 ; H, 6.24 ; N, 9.29%).

Preparation of Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (II): To Z-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (0.5 g) in acetic acid (3 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.9 ml). After one hour at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Val-ONP₃ (0.3 g). After 18 hr. at room temperature the residue was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, water, ether and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe (0.55 g, 85%), m. p. 215°-17°, R_F 0.73, [α]_D²⁰ = -77 (C=1, in D. M. F.) (found : C, 64.693 ; H, 6.35 ; N, 9.71 ; C₄₆H₅₆N₆O₁₀ requires C, 64.78 ; H, 6.57 ; N, 9.85%).

Preparation of Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OH (III): 2.4 g (2.7 m moles) of Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe was dissolved in 50 ml of anhydrous methanol, 5.4 ml of N NaOH was added and kept at 37°. After 2 hr. another 2 ml of N NaOH was added, followed in 1 hr. by 1 ml of NaOH (total is 8.4 m-moles). After a total of 4 hr. at 37° the addition of a drop of this solution to a large excess of water resulted in a clear solution. The batch was poured into 250 ml of water and acidified with dilute HCl. On standing the product crystallized out as needles (1.9 g, 75%), m. p. 223°-25°, R_F 0.79, [α]_D²⁰ = -81° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 64.57 ; H, 6.35 ; N, 9.99 ; C₄₄H₅₄N₆O₁₀ requires C, 64.43 ; H, 6.44, N, 10.02%).

Preparation of Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-ONP (IV): To Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OH (2.67 g) and p-nitrophenol

(1.67 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml) at 0° was added dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (2.06 g) and the solution was stirred at 0° for 1 hr. and then at 25° for 2 hr. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was distilled in *vacuo*. The solid residue was washed with ether (100 ml) and recrystallized from ethanol giving 3.4 g (87%) of the required product, m. p. 227°-30°, R_F 0.81, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -69^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 62.85 ; H, 6.02 ; N, 9.99 ; $C_{81}H_{87}N_7O_{10}$ requires C, 62.70 ; H, 5.84 ; N, 10.04%).

Preparation of Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂OMe (V) : To Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-OMe II (0.7 g) in acetic acid (3 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.9 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D.M.F., triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added followed by Z-L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro-ONP IV (0.4 g). After 18 hr at room temperature the residue was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, water, ether and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ OMe. (1.35g, 83%), m.p. 243°-45°, R_F 0.85, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -91^\circ$ (C=1, in D.M.F.), (found : C, 63.99 ; H, 6.75 ; N, 10.85 ; $C_{83}H_{103}N_{12}O_{18}$ requires C, 64.01 ; H, 6.61 ; N, 10.79%).

Preparation of Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂OH (VI) : 2.2 g (2.7 m moles) of Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ OMe was dissolved in 50 ml of anhydrous methanol, 5.4 ml of N NaOH was added and kept at 37°. After 2 hr. another 2 ml of N NaOH was added, followed in 1 hr. by 1 ml of N NaOH (total is 8.4 m. moles). After a total of 4 hr. at 37° the addition of a drop of this solution to a large excess of water resulted in a clear solution. The batch was foured into 250 ml of water and acidified with dilute HCl. On standing the product crystallized out as needles (1.9 g, 82%), m. p. 249°-51°, R_F 0.8, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -100^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 63.95 ; H, 6.63 ; N, 11.01 ; $C_{82}H_{101}N_{12}O_{18}$ requires C, 63.81 ; H, 6.55 ; N, 10.89%).

Preparation of Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ONP (VII) : To Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂OH (1.3 g) and *p*-nitrophenol (0.9 g) in ethyl acetate (10 ml) at 0° was added dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (1.03 g) and the solution was stirred at 0° for 1 hr. and then at 25° for 2 hr. The solution was

filtered and the filtrate was distilled in *vacuo*. The solid residue was washed with ether (100 ml) and recrystallized from ethanol giving (1.65 g, 85%) of the required product m. p. 260°-2°, R_F 0.86, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -97^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 63.02 ; H, 6.25 ; N, 11.01 ; $C_{83}H_{104}N_{13}O_{21}$ requires C, 62.89 ; H, 6.19 ; N, 10.83%).

Preparation of (L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ (VIII) : To Z(L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ ONP (0.5 g) in acetic acid (3 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (2N, 1.9 ml). After 1 hr. at room temperature dry ether was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was filtered, washed with ether and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the minimum amount of D. M. F., and triethylamine (2.6 ml) was added. After 3 days at room temperature the residue was filtered, washed with 2N HCl, 5% NaHCO₃, water ether and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give (L-Val-L-Dab (γ phth)-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ (0.24 g, 50%), m. p. 267°-9°, R_F 0.9, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -103^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 63.28 ; H, 6.75 ; N, 13.06 ; $C_{74}H_{93}N_{13}O_{17}$ requires C, 63.15 ; H, 6.61 ; N, 12.94%).

Preparation of (L-Val-L-Dab-L-Leu-D-Phe-L-Pro)₂ (IX) : The protected cyclic decapeptide (VIII) (0.5 g) was dissolved with heating in D. M. F. (4 ml). A M solution of hydrazine hydrate (1.2 ml) in D. M. F. was added. After 3 hr. the mixture was acidified with 2 N HCl, and the solvent was removed under vacuum. The residue on neutralization with Na₂CO₃ solution gave (0.37 g, 75%) of the required product. m.p. 274-6°, R_F 0.93, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -110^\circ$ (C=1, in D.M.F.), (found : C, 60.85 ; H, 7.91 ; N, 16.00 ; $C_{53}H_{89}N_{13}O_{10}$ requires C, 60.73 ; H, 7.76 ; N, 15.88%).

Amino acid analysis : L-Valine 2.01 (2 mol), L- α,γ diaminobutyric 1.98 (2 mol), Leucine 2.00 (2 mol), D-phenyl alanine 2.02 (2 mol) and proline 1.96 (2 mol).

References

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